

A Comparative Learning of Sentiment Analysis Using Machine Learning Algorithm

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Abstract— The corporate environment of today has grown extremely competitive. Growth of businesses now places a lot of emphasis on customer happiness. Business firms invest a lot of cash and labour in different ways to comprehend and meet the wants of their customers. However, due to inadequate manual examination of the varied needs of clients, many Businesses are struggling to satisfy their customers. They are thus losing their clients' loyalty and increasing their marketing expenses. Sentiment Analysis is a solution that we can use to resolve the issues. It combines machine learning with natural language processing (NLP) (ML). The goal of this research is to evaluate how well sundry machine learning algorithms analyse sentiment from Twitter data. Support vector machine, logistic regression, and Random forest algorithms performances were contrasted. The findings suggest that Random Forest has procured the highest accuracy.

Keywords:- Sentiment Analysis, Machine Learning, Support Vector machine, Logistic Regression, Random Forest, Twitter.

I. INTRODUCTION

Sentiment analysis is incorporated as a vital component of customer service for businesses on websites and online portals. They frequently do this to classify comments as a question, grievance, suggestion, opinion, or just pure adoration for a product. By doing so, they can quickly filter through the feedback or inquiries, prioritise what has to be addressed first, and even arrange them in a way that appears preponderant. Companies will occasionally even make an effort to remove content with a bad feeling attached.

Twitter is an extremely comprehensive data source for determining the value of any product. Tweets are sentences that are used on the Twitter platform to communicate opinions. As a result, sentence-level sentiment analysis is used to examine sentiments. An effective technique for businesses to learn what the public thinks about their soon-to-be-released items is through sentiment research on Twitter.

The accuracy of the sentiment of sentences obtained from tweets' text is being assessed. Sentiment analysis can be used to Twitter data, classifying each message as either positive or negative.

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Using this technique, concerned companies can discover what people's thoughts are regarding their goods, events, and more from the tweets. Businesses now use social media comments to hear from customers and do market research. Customers can voice their opinions on any product through social media. The hardest part of sentiment analysis is identifying opinion terms. Depending on the circumstance, an opinion expression could be good or negative. Traditional text processing methods won't change the information's meaning. when a slight alteration to the text has taken place. However, when there are variations between two terms, sentiment analysis can change the item's label. For instance, "This sentence is good" and "this sentence is not good" are two different statements. Sentence after sentence is processed. Twitter's informal sentence structure is understandable by the user but not by the algorithm. In this study, the effectiveness of Random Forest, Logistic Regression, and Support Vector Machine is compared.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Poornima.A, K.Sathiya Priya et al. [1]. The sentence classification algorithms Multinomial Naive Bayes, SVM, and Logistic Regression were utilised in order to contrast their efficacy. Based on the findings, it can be concluded that when combined with the n-gram and bigram models, logistic regression has the highest level of accuracy.

Md Taufiqul Haque Khan Tusar, Md. Touhidul Islam et al. [2] Comparing different ML classification methods. Based on the findings, The best methods, providing 77% accuracy, are Support Vector Machine and Logistic Regression using the Bag-of-Words strategy.

PrajvalSudhir, Varun Deshakulkarni Suresh et al.[3] Sentiment analysis is a method of extracting subjective information from textual data by identifying it in the context of the text. Users can extract critical information from online interactions using sentiment analysis, which also helps businesses analyse the social attitude toward their brand, product, or service. This essay looks into the various classification schemes and methods employed in sentiment.

analysis.

The M. A. Al-Shabi et al. [4] Five of the most notable and well-known lexicons used in sentiment analysis on Data from Twitter in this study, which uses lexicon-based sentiment analysis approaches, are the VADER, SentiWordNet, SentiStrength, Liu AFINN-111), and Hu opinion lexicons. By comparing the overall categorization accuracy and the F1-measure, it compares how well different lexicons categorise Twitter polarity. The findings indicate that the Vader Lexicon has a higher level of emotional categorization precision for both joyful and sad emotions.

The Tekendra Nath Yogi , Nawaraj Paudel etal. [5] This study's primary goal is to assess and contrast the effectiveness of three classification algorithms for sentiment-labeled data: Multinomial Naive Bayes (MNB), K Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and Support Vector Machines (SVM).sentences using three distinct datasets of varying sizes. The effectiveness of the three classification methods for In all three sentiment labelled sentence datasets in sentiment analysis, SVM is found to be a better algorithm to detect sentiment polarity.When compared to SVM, MNB and KNN perform less well in all areas than SVM.

III. PROPOSEDWORK

- 1.Accumulating data for ML classifier training and testing
2. Data preprocessing
3. Getting the model fitted and trained

Fig 1: Block diagram of the proposed work

A.DATASET DESCRIPTION

The information is organised in files with commas between the tweets and their accompanying thoughts. In the csv file containing the training dataset are tweet id, Twitter, label. A collection of words, emoticons, and symbols, URLs, and mentions of specific individuals. Added to that, the words with additional punctuation and misspelt words in them with a lot of letters repeated. Data conversion is therefore required.

preprocessing in a systematic manner.

B.PREPROCESSING

An inconsistent dataset typically results from scraping raw tweets from Twitter. This is because individuals use convivial media in a casual manner. To create a dataset that can be trained by numerous classifiers, raw twitter data must be standardised. Data is preprocessed in order to standardise the dataset and reduce its size. Preprocessed dataset is used for training and testing. Retweets, emoticons, user mentions, and other unique aspects of tweets must be successfully extracted. By using stemming, lemmatization, stopword abstraction, and other techniques, the stray information or special characters are abstracted. Preprocessing in this step includes changing the tweet's case to lower case, adding a space after two or more dots (.), Remove all spaces and quotation marks. (and) after a tweet, replacing two or more spaces with a single space, etc. Take the phrase "this product is highly flexible to use!" for instance. The final sentence after preprocessing is "product very flexible use.

C.GETTING THE MODEL FITTED AND TRAINED

1.support vector machine

A supervised machine learning technique called the Support Vector Machine (SVM) may carry out classification, regression, and even outlier detection.

2. Logistic regression

One of the most often used Machine Learning algorithms, within the category of Supervised Learning, is logistic regression. Using a predetermined set of independent factors, it is used to predict the categorical dependent variable.

3.Random forest classifier

Random Forest is a classifier that uses many decision trees on different subsets of the input dataset and averages the results to increase the dataset's predicted accuracy.

III.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to illustrate the findings of the experiments, this section compares the classification accuracy of three machine learning algorithms for sentiment analysis. accuracy_score of support vector machine is 0.9580791490692946 accuracy score of Logistic regression is 0.9486938839355545 and accuracy score Random Forest is 0.9601126231816048.

a)Support Vector machine

Fig 2: (a,b,c)Pie chart visualization of performance of different classification algorithm.

Fig 3: Comparative results

The comparison of accuracy of three machine learning algorithms is shown in Fig 3. The accuracy for Logistic regression is approximately 94.87%, Support vector machine is 95.81% and Random forest is 96.01%. Then the Random forest outperforms the SVM and Logistic regression with an accuracy

of 96.01%.

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

A technique for figuring out the perspective of a text is sentiment analysis. Social media users comment on events with their thoughts and are curious to learn whether most users had positive or negative experiences with the same event. The accuracy of the sentiment of sentences obtained from tweets' text is being assessed. When it comes to particular items, events, etc., an analysis of the sentiment of the tweet tells whether it is positive or negative. Identifying whether a word indicates a positive or negative opinion is the most difficult aspect of sentiment analysis. The parameter of a machine learning algorithm can be changed to achieve the highest accuracy. SVM, logistic regression, and random forest were three machine learning approaches whose efficacy was investigated in this study. A technique for figuring out the perspective of a text is sentiment analysis. The Random Forest has an average accuracy rating of 95.96% among social media users. Random Forest surpasses other supervised machine learning methods for sentiment analysis on Twitter. Future research is that Only three conventional machine learning-based classification algorithms have been examined in this research study for the purpose of detecting sentiment polarity in three datasets of sentiment-labeled sentences. More algorithms from the classification, clustering, and deep learning approaches may be added in the future to the datasets under study or to other datasets that include text in addition to picture, audio, or video types for additional research. Additionally, some algorithms can be tailored to the particular domain in order to improve the accuracy and dependability of sentiment analysis results.

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